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PROFILE, INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCY AND PERFORMANCE OF SEAMEO -ICEXeL COMPLETERS: BASIS FOR A PLAN OF SUSTAINABILITY

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ABSTRACT

The study used descriptive-correlational study to assess the demographic profile, competency goals and performance of the SEAMEO-ICEXeL (Instructional and Curriculum Excellence) Completers in Region III-Central Luzon; demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, civil status, number of years in the position, their position and educational attainment. The competency goals are in the five core competencies, included here are (a) strategic thinking and innovation; (b) managerial leadership; (c) instructional leadership; (d) personal excellence and (e) stakeholders' engagement. The 16 general competencies or domains were also included in the paper.

As correlational study the researcher investigated the relationship of the demographic profile and the competency goals, the profile of the respondents and their performances and lastly between the competency goals and performance.

The findings revealed that many respondents were at the age of 31- 40 years old and 41-50 years old, majority of them are female, most of them were married, majority of them serve in the present school for 1-2 years, majority were school heads and the most of them were doctoral graduates. It was also found out that the completers were distinguish in Strategic thinking and Innovation, distinguish in Managerial Leadership, as well as in Instructional Leadership, they were also distinguished in Personal Excellence and in Stakeholder's engagement; and the completers were distinguished in all domains of their performance. The results also concluded that there was a negatively strong significant correlation between civil status and strategic thinking and innovation, and negatively significant relationship between position and Instructional Leadership, there was no significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their performance and a positive significant relationship between the completers' personal excellence and performance.

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Introduction

Republic Act (RA) 9155, also known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, the School heads are clothed with the strengthened AuRA (Authority, Responsibility, and Accountability) in managing school resources such as human resources, financial resources, physical resources, and others. The RA 9155 authorizes all school heads to serve as instructional leaders and administrative administrators for their schools, based on the principles of transparency and local responsibility.

Republic Act 9155 provides explicit testimony on the instructional leadership tasks and functions of school principals. The school heads as instructional leaders provide a framework for instructional supervision and leadership to forge effective teaching-learning processes and instructional delivery to results for higher learning outcomes. As instructional leaders, the school heads provide instructional direction to all teachers in the school with a primordial purpose of improving the trajectory of effective and quality instructional delivery among teachers.

On the other note, the school heads who were defined by the RA 9155 as administrative managers in their schools are duty bound to perform their responsibilities and functions in improving the processes and mechanism of the schools in terms of its resources, linkages, and partnership with stakeholders towards effective school system in their schools. The school heads as administrative managers should be on top of managing the school resources vis-à-vis school learning outcomes.

School heads are responsible for providing quality services to their students, making them the most accountable in school management. The learners are regarded as the most significant part of the educational system. School leaders are supposed to encourage instructional innovations and creative projects, programs, and activities (PPAs) to improve school management and the instructional delivery culture among instructors, resulting in globally competitive learners and graduates.

Since education is one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the UN, school administrators have a great deal of responsibility to use creative leadership and strategic thinking to maintain partnerships and linkages with stakeholders in the community as well as to promote the welfare of teachers, students, and parents. In their capacity as administrative managers, school heads work with stakeholders and outside organizations to advance physical development and infrastructure for the benefit of students, staff, and faculty. Their collaboration is based on the shared ownership, accountability, and decision-making of the school as well as openness and truth regarding the use of resources.

Furthermore, the school heads who were vested with instructional leaders should be knowledgeable in providing technical expertise to improve teachers' competencies towards effective instructional delivery through supportive and motivating instructional leadership approaches. Additionally, well-rounded school administrators use a variety of leadership philosophies that are tailored to the demands of their teachers' instruction and areas in which they fall short. Thus, classroom leadership is a means of establishing and conveying a clear educational vision and objectives to both educators and learners, as well as providing coaching, mentorship, and professional development for educators (Robinson, Lloyd, & Rowe, 2018).

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Strong instructional leadership among school heads can have a favorable impact on students' academic achievement and school learning outcomes, according to an article published in 2014 by Carraway and Young. Therefore, the goal of the instructional leadership model is to encourage better learning outcomes for students, which can be achieved by enhancing the management and leadership skills of school administrators.

On the other note, school heads of Region III- Central Luzon composed of twenty Schools Divisions attended the series of SEAMEO-ICEXeL (Instructional and Curriculum Excellence) for the last 2 school years (SY 2020-2021 and SY 2021-2022) through online platform to propel the instructional competence of the school heads by equipping them with the necessary competencies and skills to lead and manage schools. Furthermore, SEAMEO-ICEXeL (Instructional and Curriculum Excellence) is one of the Flagship Programs of DepEd-Region III- Central Luzon to further hone the school leadership and managerial competencies of the school heads.

Methods

The study used descriptive-correlational research design. It is descriptive because it describes a given situation or condition in terms of specific effects or factors. This kind of research supplies a thorough and precise picture of the characteristics and behaviors of a particular population or subject (Sirisilla, 2023). Descriptive research design supports a paper to gain a deeper understanding of a definite subject and gives valuable insights.

As descriptive research designs this study, described the demographic profile of the SEAMEO-ICEXeL (Instructional and Curriculum Excellence) Completers in Region III- Central Luzon by identifying the age, sex, civil status, number of years in the current position, position and educational attainment. The competency goals and performance were also analyzed and described using the Likert Scale with verbal description. The competency goals were illustrated with the Competency Framework for Southeast Asian School Heads comprises of five (5) core competencies, Strategic thinking and innovation, Managerial leadership, Instructional leadership, Personal excellence and Stakeholder engagement. Meanwhile, the performance of the SEAMEO-ICEXeL completers relied on 16 general competencies of competency goals of the respondents.

In this descriptive correlational study, the researcher also investigated the relationship between the respondents' performance and competency goals, their performance and demographic profile, and their goals and performance.

The suggested action plan to offer instructional support for the SEAMEO-ICEXeL completers was developed based on the study's findings.

Results and Discussions

1. Demographic Profile

The term "demographics" denotes the distinctive characteristics that are present within a particular group. The term encompasses criteria such as geographic region, income level, and age. Focus groups, surveys and questionnaires, census collection,

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and psychographic research are among the numerous methods for collecting demographic data.

1.1 Age of the respondents

Respondents of all ages, nationalities, and races may view life from different perspectives. It is feasible to do a more in-depth study of your findings by combining age groups for survey data with relevant survey questions. It may also help you fine-tune your sample process.

Khan, 1991 claims that when an individual reaches a certain age, he or she becomes intellectually mature and capable of making sensible decisions. Table 1 shows the ages of the respondents.

As seen in Table 1 12 or 39% of the respondents were 31-40 and 41-50 of age. While there were 6 or 19 percent of respondents were 51-60 and 1 or 3% of the respondents were 20-30 years old.

One of the many repercussions of an aging population is that older people are more likely than ever to hold positions of leadership. Psychological research has

concluded that there are specific traits that older leaders have in common with those of younger leaders. After reviewing the research, Truxillo and Burlacu (2015) concluded that a leader's or subordinate's age can have a significant effect on how they view and communicate with one another.

Table 1

Age of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	%
20-30	1	3
31-40	12	39
41-50	12	39
51-60	6	19
Total	31	

1.2 Sex of the Respondents

The findings of the research can be influenced by the sex of the participants. There is a probability that the sex of the respondents will influence the conclusions of the research. The term "sex" has been in use since the 1920s, and it is appropriate to use it to categorize people based on their reproductive systems. The terms "male" and "female" are sex categories that describe the physical and mental differences between the sexes. Table 2 presents the sex of the respondents.

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Table 2
Sex of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	%
Male	11	35
Female	20	65
Total	31	

Table 2 shows the distribution of sexes. Of the 31 responders, the table reveals that 20 (65%) are female and 11 (35%) are male. Women are becoming more and more powerful in sectors like psychology, higher education, business, and Congress. The world still boasts a sizable number of male and female leaders, notwithstanding a few exceptions. This phrase has been used for years by well-known psychologists, most notably the late Jean Lau Chin, EdD, the first Asian American psychologist licensed in the state of Massachusetts and a trailblazer in the battle for more diversity in positions of leadership.

According to research, when compared to males, females perform significantly better on exams that measure recollection. They have an advantage when it comes to the speed at which they can perform activities that involve letters, numerals, and quick naming. Object location memory and verbal memory are skills that are often more developed in females. They are also more effective when it comes to verbal learning. It has been found that females are more adept at matching items and performing precision tasks, such as inserting pegs into holes that have been specified for them. The number of trials required for males to learn the objective route in labyrinth and path completion tasks is lower than that required for females; nevertheless, females remember more of the landmarks that are given. According to this, it appears that females are more likely than males to use landmarks in everyday circumstances in order to orient themselves. The ability of females to remember whether or not things had shifted positions was superior to that of males.

1.1 Civil Status of the Respondents

The term "civil status" refers to the legal and social status of an individual within a given society. This position is determined by the individual's personal characteristics, such as their gender, age, marital status, and religious beliefs.

The Civil Status of the respondents is presented in table 3.

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Table 3

The Civil status of the Respondents

Civil Status	Frequency	%
Single	9	29
Married	21	68
Widow/er	0	0
Separated	1	3
Total	31	

Table 3 shows that the majority of respondents are married (21 or 68%), whereas 9 or 29% are single, 1 or 3% are separated, and there is no widower. As a result, it is reasonable to presume that the majority of respondents' civil status is married.

CEO positions in larger companies, knowledge-based industries, and complex operations are better suited for married couples. According to more research, when a married couple's CEO has a high degree of education, their age difference is minimal, and one of the spouses is willing to run the company, marital leadership has a considerable impact on firm success. Marital leadership has the potential to enhance company success because to all three of these reasons. In the Philippines, the only acknowledged civil status categories are typically Single, Married, Widowed, or Legally Separated. Any deviation from these recognized categories may be regarded as misleading and legally void.

According to the findings of Amore et al. (2017), family businesses that are led by married couples have much superior performance than other types of family company leadership configurations.

1.2 Number of years managing the present school of the Respondents

Managing the school refers to the process of planning, coordinating, and directing activities inside a school through the efficient utilization of both human and material resources in order to achieve the goals of the school is referred to as school administration. Table 4 presents the number of years that the respondents managed the school.

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Table 4

Number of years managing the present school of the Respondents

No. of years managing the present school of the Respondents	Frequency	%
7 years and up	6	13
5-6	6	13
3-4	10	33
1-2	11	35
Total	31	

Table 4 shows the number of years managing the present school of the respondents. Data revealed above and as listed by the respondents 11 (35%) of the total respondents served their present school in 1-2 years, while there were 10 (33%) respondents who were serving their school in 3-4 years. Further, it can be seen in table 4 that 5-6 range and 7 years up have the same frequency of 6 or 13%. As a result of this data, most of the respondents were serving their present school for 1-2 years. This distribution is recognized and may be utilized as a representation of experienced educators who possess the necessary information and knowledge for the study.

The number of years in managing the school has an impact on the leadership, management and supervision of the school. It is the responsibility of educational administrators to oversee financial matters, logistics, timetables, disciplinary measures, assessments, and public relations. Leadership is provided by school administrators, who also paint a positive picture of the future of the institutions they oversee.

1.5 Position of the Respondents

A set of professional standards for head teachers and principals is established by the Department of Education (DepEd). These standards outline the professional practice that is expected of a qualified head teacher and principal. All human resource systems, policies, guidelines, and mechanisms, including those about school head recruitment, placement, performance evaluation, rewards, and recognition, as well as talent management, must be based on the PPSSH. Table 5 presents the Position of the respondents.

Table 5

Position of the Respondents

Position of the Respondents	Frequency	%
Head Teacher	17	55
Principal	14	45
Total	31	

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Table 5 indicates the respondents' positions; according to the data gathered, there were 17 (55%) head teachers and 14 (45%) principals. According to the findings, the majority of responders were head teachers. The head teachers have extensive experience and hence include the necessary information for the study.

According to experts, the head teachers play a significant part in ensuring that the education that is provided by the school is of a high standard. As educational leaders, facilitators, and managers, they are responsible for guiding and managing the implementation of highly effective instructional approaches.

School principals oversee ensuring that all areas of the school are in order, as well as that everyone in the school works successfully, efficiently, and collaboratively. In a similar spirit, outstanding school principals are excellent educators who focus their attention on core issues such as learning, teaching, and the school's continued growth. School leaders are responsible for guiding their institutions through the goal-setting process, which includes analyzing data on student achievement, identifying areas for development, and implementing change initiatives.

1.6 Educational Attainment of the Respondents

The term "educational attainment" refers to the education level that an individual has finished at the greatest possible degree. There is a distinction between this and the level of education that an individual is currently pursuing. Table 6 presents the Position of the respondents.

Table 6

Educational Attainment of the Respondents

Educational Attainment	Frequency	%
Doctoral Graduates	13	42
Doctoral with units	9	29
Masteral Graduates	5	16
Masteral with units	4	13
4-year course	0	0
Total	31	

Table 6 presents the data on the Educational Attainment of the respondents. Data revealed that among the 31 respondents 13 (42%) of them have finished their doctorate degree, while 9 (29%) of the respondents earned units in their doctorate degree. Further, it can be seen from table 6 that 5 (16%) of the respondents finished their masteral degree and 4 (13%) were identified as respondents who just earned their masteral units.

Card (2001), and Heckman et al. (2003, 2018) are just few of the studies that have been conducted in the field of labor economics that have concluded that earning a college degree is associated with a persistent and significant rise in both employment and pay. When it comes to the hiring process and other agencies, the educational background of individuals is an extremely important factor.

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Seifert (2023) explained in his study that the higher levels of educational attainment are related with a number of characteristics, including better levels of intellect, improved communication skills, and more developed cognitive capacities. These characteristics are also linked to effective political leadership.

2. SEAMEO -ICEXeL Completers' Competency Goals

2.1 Strategic Thinking and Innovation of the Respondents

The term "strategic thinking" refers to a deliberate and rational process of thinking, with a major focus on the evaluation of critical features and variables that will influence an organization's, group's, or individual's long-term performance.

One definition of innovation is "the process of enhancing or replacing something," which could be a process, product, or service. Strategic thinking and innovation are the ability to define the school's strategic direction, make informed decisions, and promote change and innovation. Table 7 summarizes the respondents' strategic thinking and innovation.

**Table 7
Strategic Thinking and Innovation**

Strategic Thinking and Innovation		
Indicator	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Work with the school and community stakeholders in developing a school strategic plan	3.97	Distinguished
2. Lead in the implementation of the strategic plan	3.94	Distinguished
3. Demonstrate the school's vision and model the values in everyday work and practice	3.74	Distinguished
4. Use a range of evidence to support, monitor, evaluate and improve the strategic plan	3.87	Distinguished
5. Practice regular review of the plan/program implementation and utilize results in addressing implementation concerns and issues	3.84	Distinguished
6. Lead the change process toward the development and implementation of new	3.94	Distinguished

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approaches, systems and structures.		
7. Sustain creativity and innovation in school programs to achieve higher learning outcomes	3.71	Distinguished
Weighted Mean	3.86	Distinguished

An overview of the strategic thinking and creativity of the respondents is shown in Table 7. Schools that adopt a strong strategic plan and commit to strategic planning in education have a significant advantage over schools that do not pursue these strategies, according to the respondents, who rated the work with the school and community stakeholders in developing a school strategic plan as "distinguished" with a mean of 3.97.

Additionally, with a mean score of 3.94, respondents think that the Lead in the development and implementation of new techniques, processes, and structures is distinct from the Lead in the implementation of the strategic plan.

Schools need to make sure that everyone who has a stake in the matter—parents, educators, administrators, principals, board members, and members of the community—has the same vision. Effective planning and communication are key to achieving this, as they guarantee that all parties involved agree with these objectives. Additionally, schools gain the most from the practice of regularly reviewing performance when it comes to implementing those goals, and this practice may be established with the aid of a strategic plan.

In a similar vein, participants "distinguished" between the ways in which different types of evidence are used to monitor, assess, and refine the strategic plan. If evaluations are purposefully created to support cycles of management activity, including planning, budgeting, analysis, program execution, and benefits reporting and communication, they can be advantageous as well as economical.

Additionally, respondents "distinguished" the practice of regularly evaluating the implementation of plans and programs and applying the findings to address implementation challenges and concerns with an average score of 3.87. Periodic evaluations are conducted to appraise advancement and implement any necessary modifications to the action plan to guarantee that the group persists in achieving the project's goals.

Furthermore, respondents "distinguished" (3.74) the demonstration of the school's vision and model of values in everyday work and practice. A school's identity is established by its Vision and Mission, which clearly and concisely describe the institution's fundamental values, goals, and aspirations. They establish appropriate purpose and direction, which defines the culture, educational techniques, and relationships that exist inside the community. This contributes to the development of a distinct identity that serves as a guiding concept for all activities and decisions made at the school.

Finally, the respondents "**distinguished**" (3.71) in the Sustaining creativity and innovation in school programs to achieve higher learning outcomes. By being innovative

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and imaginative, we can have a deeper comprehension of various subjects. Schools foster the development of thinkers who can make use of their own talents in order to investigate a wide range of interests by employing a manner of instruction that is creative and exploratory.

Mallari (2022) Planning is a preparatory step that involves thinking forward and defining potential future courses of action before acting. A detailed plan course of action is what we mean when we talk about planning. It is a methodical process that outlines when, how, and who will carry out a specific task so that it can be completed. To be successful as a school administrator, it is essential to have the ability to plan. These are the kinds of qualities that are necessary for a good leader to possess in order to effectively manage the school.

In Summary, the respondents rated Strategic Thinking and Innovation with the grand mean of **3.86** and a verbal description of **distinguished**. It is evident that the respondents strategic thinking is at the level of they can do things with confidence and at the same time can teach their subordinates to have the same skills in strategic thinking and innovation. Hence, it is necessary to receive trainings to maintain the skills and even elevate to advance their performance.

2.2 Managerial Leadership of the Respondents

Refers to the capacity to oversee personnel performance, oversee school systems and resources, and oversee long-term initiatives and activities. Being able to cope with a variety of situations that can influence leadership skills in order to be a school head. To lead, one needs to have the ability to lead and exhibit managerial skills. It is possible for leaders to easily manage the school if you possess strong management skills and experience. Table 8 presents the Strategic Thinking and Innovation of the respondents

Table 8
Managerial Leadership of the Respondents

Managerial Leadership		
Indicator	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Manage the learning environment	3.84	Distinguished
2. Manage systems and procedures	3.81	Distinguished
3. Manage school personnel requirements	3.84	Distinguished
4. Support professional development of staff	3.90	Distinguished
5. Recognize staff performance	3.87	Distinguished

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6. Demonstrate program, and project management skills	3.77	Distinguished
7. Promote school-based programs and projects that support sustainable development.	3.94	Distinguished
Weighted Mean	3.85	Distinguished

The Respondents' Managerial Leadership is delineated in Table 8. The respondents "distinguished" (3.94) to support school-based initiatives and activities that advance sustainable development, according to the data. It takes more than just keeping a program going to be sustainable; the leader needs to build habits, connections, and practices that the community will carry forward into the future. This is because the concept of sustainability is not straightforward. It is appropriate for a leader to oversee the school and support initiatives and activities that are sustainable.

Additionally, the responders are "distinguished" with 3.90 refers to supporting staff members' professional development. Professional development encompasses a variety of activities, including career training and continuing education. Once in the workforce, professional development is the process of learning new skills. Engaging in events like visiting conferences for professionals or business, going to seminars or workshops, or earning a diploma to broaden one's knowledge in a selected field. As the organization's leader, it is critical that you promote the need for professional development for all of the staff members and teachers.

In addition, the respondents "**distinguished**" (3.87) to Recognize the staff performance. The simple act of acknowledging success can have a significant impact on both the morale and performance of employees. Studies conducted by Gallup have demonstrated that the primary performance indicators utilized to evaluate schools are directly influenced by the continuous recognition of exemplary performance. From a performance perspective, it is clear that schools are not operating at their full potential when exceptional educators are neglected to recognize.

Suliman (2019), also confirmed that talent management and employee recognition are interconnected factors that have an impact on employee performance. The management of talent and the performance of people are both considered to be strategic instruments that can be used to accomplish strategic objectives and improve the performance of both employees and the organization.

Data shows that the respondents rated **3.84** mean to Manage the school personnel requirements is considered "**distinguished**" in this area. The SEAMEO ICExeL completers are leaders who can breakdown and classified personnel roles and responsibilities to maximize the efforts of the personnel for optimum performance,

Likewise, the respondents are "**distinguished**" to Manage the learning environment has **3.84** mean. Conduct an inspection of the facilities and equipment to determine whether or not they are appropriate for the programmed.

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Based on the results, the respondents "**distinguished**" (3.81) the Manage systems and procedures. Create management methods that encourage communication, collaboration, and learning throughout the entire institution, and make sure they persist. As a principal they have skills in managing the school and the whole core of the organization. Data reveals that the principals take the courage to have a good communication skill, collaboration with the community and linkages.

The data reveals that respondents "**distinguished**" (3.77) in Demonstration of the program and project management skills. In order to foster communication, cooperation, and learning throughout the entire organization, it is necessary to establish and sustain management procedures and programs for the school. The supervision and evaluation of the implementation of projects and programs is something that should be done.

In Summary, the SEAMEO ICExeL completers **Managerial Leadership** weighted mean with 3.85 and with verbal description of **distinguished**. Establishing a managerial leadership style can have a significant impact on the performance of the personnel. For various sorts of groupings to flourish, different managerial leadership styles are required. The ability to have a better impact over coworkers and to inspire them in a way that leads to successful outcomes, this can be improved by developing unique managerial leadership style.

2.3 Instructional Leadership of the Respondents

Define it as the ability to supervise and evaluate teachers' performance, create a learner-centered environment, oversee curriculum implementation and improvement, and carry out predefined learning outcomes. Recent study on school leadership has highlighted the significance of principals' organizational management skills, motivating scholars to investigate their relationship to instructional leadership attributes. Table 9 summarizes the Respondents' Instructional Leadership.

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Table 9

Instructional Leadership of the Respondents

Instructional Leadership		
Indicator	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Manage curriculum implementation	3.90	Distinguished
2. Promote sensitivity towards diversity and differentiated instruction	3.81	Distinguished
3. Promote learner-centered activities	3.94	Distinguished
4. Promote a healthy, safe and inclusive learning environment	3.84	Distinguished
5. Promote a culture of peace and respect for diversity	3.90	Distinguished
6. Apply appropriate models to supervision and evaluation	3.84	Distinguished
7. Nurture teacher-leaders	3.90	Distinguished
8. Promote team-based approaches to instructional leadership	3.90	Distinguished
9. Manage assessment to improve teaching and learning	3.74	Distinguished
Weighted Mean	3.86	Distinguished

Table 9 shows the instructional leadership of the respondents. The above data demonstrated by the SEAMEO ICExeL completers shows that they are “**distinguished**” (3.94) to Promote learner-centered activities. The educational approach known as student-centered learning places the students at the center of the learning process, making them the primary focus of the learning process. It only shows that in the respective school of the completers the learner-centered is achieved. A student-centered education is known to have several benefits which are associated, including increased levels of engagement and motivation, improved capabilities in critical

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thinking and problem-solving, increased levels of autonomy, and individualized educational experiences.

The data shows that the respondents “**distinguished**” (3.90) to Manage the curriculum implementation. These only show that the SEAMEO ICeXeL completers can implement the curriculum programs by providing various teaching and learning activities, and evaluation and supervision to assess and monitor the improvement and efficiency of the curriculum.

The mean of 3.90 indicates that the participants are “distinguished” in their efforts to foster a culture of peace and tolerance for diversity. It illustrates that as leaders, the graduates are role models for peace, able to nurture peace within themselves and foster peace in schools. One of the goals of SEAMEO Innotech is for their completers to develop a sense of peace and respect for cultural diversity within themselves, and to equip them with competencies for championing peace in their school and community (SEAMEO INNOTECH, 2011).

The completers are also “**distinguished**” (3.90) to Nurture teacher-leaders, This is the ability to empower the teachers. As a principal, it is their responsibility to make an environment where students and teachers are supported and empowered to take rights and own of the learning of the students and teachers, and professional development for the teachers. This is also fostering a value of collective decision-making, collaboration, and responsibility, and creating a place where everyone feels confident in their capability to take the lead and grow.

Likewise, the completers are “**distinguished**” (3.90) to Promote team-based approaches to instructional leadership. A team-based style of leadership believes that everyone in the team is held equally responsible for the quality and success of the school. The leader is focused on building strong and collaborative teams of teachers and staff that work together to achieve common goals.

These four indicators rated with a mean of **3.90** and verbal description of **distinguished**, revealed that Management of the curriculum is important in the school management.

Management, as defined by Henri Fayol, is comprised of the following activities: forecasting, planning, organizing, commanding, coordinating, and controlling. It is an operational process that is initially disassembled and tackled by doing an analysis of the roles which management performs. According to Gryphon (2000), management is the process of utilizing the resources of an organization to accomplish its objectives in a manner that is both productive and efficient.

Based on the results, the respondents “**distinguished**” (3.84) Promote a healthy, safe, and inclusive learning environment. Creating a secure environment that is inclusive of children with various learning styles, genders, races, religions, and ethnicities requires a substantial amount of time beyond the initial month of resuming our classroom activities. Inclusive teaching techniques refer to a diverse set of teaching methods that can be employed to educate students with disabilities. It reveals that inclusive education is needed and to attain the proposed program we need to accept the diverse backgrounds, talents, and learning styles of students.

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Likewise, **distinguished (3.84)** to Apply appropriate models to supervision and evaluation. The primary function of models and evaluation is for the teacher to have appropriate representation for them to follow and for the development of the teachers.

In addition, the data shows that the respondents were **“distinguished” (3.81)** in Promoting sensitivity towards diversity and differentiated instruction. Differentiated instruction is a promising strategy that offers a flexible framework to accommodate these differences. Differentiated instruction can help promote the construction of learning environments that are more inclusive and efficient (Gheysens et al., 2023). This is accomplished by adjusting teaching techniques, content, and evaluations to fit an array of students' various requirements.

Likewise, it reveals that the Manage assessments to improve teaching and learning was **“distinguished” (3.74)**. The information that instructors obtain from assessments provides them with the foundational tools they need to develop individualized instructional plans for students who are having difficulty learning. It is possible to combine several different aspects into the process of customizing a student's plan. One of these aspects is a mechanism that allows for the monitoring and evaluation of the growth of the child, the instructor, and the families that are engaged. The design of the strategy, on the other hand, may be drastically different from one instance to the next.

As a Summary, it shows that the respondents “distinguish” the Instructional Leadership of the Respondents with a weighted mean of 3.86. Increasing the students' capacity to collaborate successfully with others, to deal with unfamiliar situations by employing advanced thinking, and to effectively solve obstacles by making use of the knowledge they have received, which ultimately results in improved outcomes.

2.4 Personal Excellence of the Respondents

Describe as the willingness to control one's own effectiveness, take advantage of opportunities and difficulties, and pursue ongoing professional development. Achieving personal excellence is the goal of personal progress. Consequently, a leader achieved mastery of both them and their actions. This will give awareness of what the leaders can do and how to execute it. Table 10 presents the Instructional Leadership of the Respondents.

Table 10
Personal Excellence of the Respondents

Personal Excellence		
Indicator	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Lead by example	3.81	Distinguished
2. Demonstrate transparency and accounting	3.87	Distinguished

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3. Practice a balance healthy lifestyle	3.87	Distinguished
4. Take pride in one's profession	3.87	Distinguished
5. Deliver Results	3.77	Distinguished
6. Manage Priorities	3.74	Distinguished
7. Exhibits an enterprising attitude	3.87	Distinguished
8. Exhibit an enterprising attitude	3.74	Distinguished
9. Take responsibility for one's own lifelong learning	3.84	Distinguished
10. Advocate ASEAN values and perspectives	3.84	Distinguished
Weighted Mean	3.82	Distinguished

Table 10 shows the Personal Excellence of the respondents. As stated by the respondents, with a mean of **3.87** this indicates that they are **“distinguished”** by the Demonstration of transparency and accounting. This can be displayed through the transparency board of each school. As a reflection of the finances of the school and at the same time the showcase of the activities affects their excellence, specifically, in transparency and accounting.

As part of their Excellence, the SEAMEO IEXCeL completers are also **“distinguished” (3.87)** in this area, practicing a balanced, healthy lifestyle. This indicates that as part of their personal excellence they ensure that they have a balanced and healthy lifestyle and the same time being **“distinguished”** means that they can share and transform their subordinates to have the same practiced.

Likewise, a mean 3.87 was garnered to Take pride in one's profession makes the completers **“distinguished”** in taking pride in their, they are satisfied with their contributions to the success of the school. They also value their efforts to help learners and personnel to support their school to provide quality education.

The SEAMEO IEXCeL completers, as part of their personal Excellence, are also **“distinguished” (3.87)** to Exhibit decisiveness in addressing challenges. This indicates that the completers can undertake different challenges. They can discern the action to take in every specific and unique challenges and adversity in managing the school

The above four indicators got the mean of 3. 87 and a verbal description of **distinguished**. Because of the ethical value that they have advocate immediately instills a sense of comfort in your clientele, transparency results in an increase in the level of trust and they will be expected to perform their duty with the same amount of care and

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diligence as everyone else. As a leader it is a must that you have good credibility and integrity as they lead the community and the school.

It shows that the respondents **"distinguished"** (3.84) to Take responsibility for one's own lifelong learning. Lifelong learning is a form of education that individuals actively pursue in order to enhance their personal growth and development. Lifelong learning is a word that lacks a universally agreed upon definition, although it often refers to the act of gaining knowledge and skills outside of formal educational institutions, such as schools, universities, or corporate training programmes.

Tekkol and Demirel (2018) investigated the correlation between the self-directed learning abilities of university students and their inclination towards lifelong learning. The findings indicated that the self-directed learning scores of university students exceeded the median score of the scale. Self-directed learning skills were found to be consistent across universities, years of study, and income levels. Therefore, individuals must engage in lifelong learning in order to keep up with and adapt to the ever-changing nature of life and the market, both of which are highly dynamic. Individuals can increase their degree of expertise by participating in continual education, whether through extended, moderate, or brief educational courses.

The respondents are also **"distinguished"** (3.84) to Advocate ASEAN values and perspectives. ASEAN supports global and regional commitments in education by promoting lifelong learning underpinned by the principles of equity, inclusion and quality (asean.org, 2024). Advocating the ASEAN values and perspective is also believing with the education system.

The data revealed that the respondents **"distinguished"** (3.81) to Lead by example. Students and children are extremely susceptible to being influenced, and they are actively looking for role models whose behaviors they will learn to imitate and embrace. Because of this, it is essential for you, as a teacher, to set a good example for your students and motivate them to achieve their full potential.

In addition, it is possible that you can assist in encouraging and directing your students to attain their goals by simply exhibiting these characteristics that you already possess and by reaffirming to your students that qualities such as these are valuable. It is not necessary to be a dictator and rule with an iron fist to be a leader; all that is required of you is to inspire, and that is precisely what you do when you are a teacher.

It shows that the respondents **"distinguished"** (3.77) to Deliver results. It is the responsibility of principals to ensure that students receive instruction of the highest possible quality. A principal's ability to make an influence at their school is greatly enhanced by the strategic use of data. Nevertheless, it is insufficient to merely accept the data at its value. In order to understand the rationale behind a trend, the most effective principals will probe the data. Rather than reacting hastily to poor data, this more thorough examination of the facts leads to decisions of good quality. The importance of being proactive rather than reactive may be learned by all of us.

The least mean under the Personal Excellence was 3.74, first to Manage priorities and second Exhibit an enterprising attitude. This means that the completers are **"distinguished"** in managing their priorities. Managing school imposed a lot limits, limits on time, budget, staff and other resources, hence, it is crucial for the leaders to manage

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their priorities. Confronted with these limitations and the various objectives leaders are still needed to achieve, setting priorities is vital to achieve the objective of the school.

Relatively, the “**distinguished**” Enterprising attitude can help the respondents to manage their priorities. As the leaders thought of the priorities, they can also consider the economic ways to decide what are the priorities.

As a summary it shows that respondents personal excellence weighted mean **3.82** and verbally describe as “**distinguished**”. It revealed that respondent's personal excellence has an impact on the leadership of the respondents, which means that the respondents need to maintain or enhance this category.

2.5 Stakeholders' Engagement of the Respondents

Explain the capability to foster shared accountability for school reform, oversee networks and alliances for education, and maintain cooperative connections with stakeholders.

The term "stakeholder engagement" refers to the methodical approach that educational institutions adopt in order to successfully interact with and develop an understanding of its stakeholders. The schools are able to gain a more in-depth grasp of the students' desires, timing preferences, degree of involvement, and the possible impact that the firms' tactics and efforts could have on their goals if they familiarize themselves with the students. Table 11 presents the Stakeholders' Engagement of the Respondents.

Table 11
Stakeholders' Engagement of the Respondents

Stakeholders' Engagement		
Indicator	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Build trust and lead teams/ communities for school improvement	3.87	Distinguished
2. Empower the community to work for the enhancement of school performance	3.90	Distinguished
3. Communicate effectively with different stakeholders	3.71	Distinguished
4. Facilitate school community partnerships and activities	3.87	Distinguished
5. Promote consensus-building	3.94	Distinguished
6. Manage conflict and practice negotiation skills	3.74	Distinguished

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7. Support community-based programs and projects	3.94	Distinguished
8. Communicate school performance to the stakeholders	3.81	Distinguished
Weighted Mean	3.85	Distinguished

Table 11 shows the Stakeholders' Engagement of the respondents. It shows that the respondents rated this indicator as **distinguished** with a mean of **3.94** where the respondents promote consensus-building and Support community-based programs and projects. In this data, consensus, in essence, refers to a broad consensus reached by two or more stakeholders. For school districts and other large organizations, implementing widespread reforms is essential. It is necessary to guarantee that all persons attain a state of general agreement to develop consensus. This will allow for the establishment of important decisions and their subsequent implementation. To do this, it is vital to consider each individual's distinct aspirations. This consensus will also serve as a support activity for community-based activities.

Furthermore, the statistics show that respondents "distinguished" (3.90) the Empowerment of the Community to Work for the Improvement of School Performance. Community empowerment is the process of granting communities' greater authority and control over their own lives. "Communities" are groupings of individuals who, albeit not necessarily physically linked, share common interests, concerns, or identities. These communities can exist at the local, national, or global levels, and their interests may be specific or wide. Empowerment is the process by which individuals gain control and influence over the various aspects and decisions that shape their lives. It pertains to the act of individuals or organizations improving their resources, skills, and talents to obtain chances, form partnerships, broaden networks, and exercise influence in order to gain control. It is implied by the phrase "enabling" that individuals cannot be enabled by forces from the outside; rather, they can only empower themselves by obtaining a variety of sources of strength. The reference that was provided comes from the work that Laverack (2008).

Community empowerment refers to the process of redefining power dynamics in order to attain greater control. The statement acknowledges that when certain persons are strengthened, others will have to relinquish a portion of the power they already hold (Baum, 2008).

Furthermore, developing trust and guiding teams/communities to improve schools, as well as facilitating school-community connections and activities. Respondents ranked these factors as differentiated with a mean of 3.87, indicating that further development and improvement is required.

Through community partnerships, schools and other organizations and groups include families in meaningful and culturally relevant ways. Families actively participate in their children's growth and education through this process, and schools and other community agencies and organizations share accountability and gain from it as well. By actively listening to them, offering support, and giving them the tools they need to

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participate in their children's education in a responsible manner, schools and community organizations hope to actively involve parents in their children's education.

Furthermore, the table indicates that respondents "distinguish" (3.81) between communicating school performance to stakeholders. Stakeholders in education include both active participants, such as parents, instructors, and students, and those who are indirectly impacted by an educational system's success or failure, such as government officials and local business leaders. Data suggests that it is vital to properly connect with stakeholders and describe the school's needs and performance in order to inspire active engagement.

Additionally, the data shows that the respondents of the study "**distinguished**" (3.74) between managing the conflict and practicing negotiation skills. It reveals that as a leader you have the skills in negotiation dealing with others and resolving conflicts. Herry (2024) Negotiation is a dialogue between two or more parties to achieve a mutually agreeable solution. Ultimately, it may culminate in a formal arrangement, such as a legally binding contract, or it may manifest as a more informal comprehension, such as a verbal agreement. If you possess a comprehensive comprehension of the mechanics of negotiations and the requisite aptitudes, you stand a chance of acquiring a beneficial resolution.

Lastly, it reveals that the respondents "**distinguished**" (3.71) to Communicate effectively with different stakeholders. Maintaining ongoing communication with stakeholders over the whole duration of a project facilitates enhanced coordination and alignment. To ensure that deadlines are adhered to, and budgets are maintained, it is crucial to consistently update stakeholders on the progress, challenges, and significant achievements during the project.

As a Summary of the Stakeholders' Engagement, it shows that the respondents have a good engagement with the stakeholders as the weighted mean of **3.87** and verbally describe as **distinguished**.

3. Performance of the Respondents

Performance refers to the action of carrying out a task or activity, particularly when it is done well. It involves the practical application of knowledge rather than just having knowledge. Table 12 presents the Performance of the respondents.

Table 12

Performance of the Respondents

Domain	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Charting the strategic Directions of the school	3.87	Distinguished
2. Making informed Decisions	3.87	Distinguished
3. Leading change and innovations	3.77	Distinguished

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4. Managing school resources and systems	3.84	Distinguished
5. Managing staff performance	3.97	Distinguished
6. Managing sustainable school programs and projects	3.90	Distinguished
7. Leading Curriculum implementation and improvement	3.77	Distinguished
8. Creating a learner-centered environment	3.87	Distinguished
9. Supervising and evaluating teacher's performance	3.90	Distinguished
10. Delivering planned learning outcomes	4.00	Distinguished
11. Managing personal effectiveness	3.87	Distinguished
12. Acting on challenges and possibilities	3.97	Distinguished
13. Pursuing continuous professional Development	3.84	Distinguished
14. Promoting shared responsibilities for school improvement.	3.90	Distinguished
15. Managing education alliance and networks	3.90	Distinguished
16. Sustaining collaboration with relationship and stakeholders	3.87	Distinguished
Weighted Mean	3.88	Distinguished

Table 12 shows the data on the Performance of the Respondents. The data reveals that the respondents “**distinguished**” (4.0) in Delivering planned and learning outcomes. Learning outcomes refer to the explicit statements that describe the specific knowledge or skills that students are expected to have learned upon completion of an assignment, class, course, or program. The table shows that Effective learning outcomes prioritize the practical application and integration of gained knowledge. The

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respondents should focus more on the delivery of the Learning outcomes, both in the classroom and beyond, rather than simply the content itself.

In addition, the results show that the respondents **“distinguished” (3.9)** in Managing Staff performance and Acting on challenges and possibilities. Research findings have shown that effective management enhances employee engagement, amplifies productivity, and nurtures professional development. The subsequent illustration illustrates that effective management is a continuous process that requires persistent and constant effort.

Further, the respondents to this study must have the skills to manage properly the performance of the staff to ensure the proper productivity and engagement of everyone.

Additionally, the tables demonstrate that respondents "distinguished" (3.87) themselves in four domains: overseeing and assessing teacher performance, encouraging shared accountability for school development, managing education alliances and networks, and managing sustainable school programs and projects. Managing sustainable school programs and projects involves the strategic planning, execution, and evaluation of educational activities that support the long-term prosperity of schools and communities. These projects are specifically crafted to foster sustainability and enhance the prosperity of schools and communities it reveals that it is so important to have the skills in managing the sustainable programs of the school and to have the skills in supervising and evaluating the performance of the teachers and the schools' activities.

Furthermore, the statistics suggest that respondents "distinguished" (3.87) in charting the school's strategic directions, making informed judgments, providing a learner-centered environment, managing personal effectiveness, and maintaining engagement with partners and stakeholders. An educational technique known as student-centered learning is one in which the learning methods and objectives are focused on the experiences, curiosity, and interests of the students themselves: the students themselves. The essence of the matter is that students have the authority to decide not just the subject matter of their education but also how they gain knowledge. It also reveals that having a sustaining collaborative relationship and connection with the stakeholders will help the school gain new development and will have a good relationship within the community.

Furthermore, according to the respondent's data, managing school resources and processes and pursuing ongoing professional development are "distinguishable" (3.84). As the institution's administrator, it is your duty to guarantee that the school runs smoothly and successfully. Because of this, you need to be able to manage the school's resources well in order to make sure that everything runs smoothly and that kids have enough access to the tools they need to excel in school.

Lastly, the results describe the respondents **“distinguished” (3.77)** in Leading change and innovations and Leading curriculum implementation and improvement. The respondents are responsible for managing the curriculum, altering any organizational structures that may obstruct effective practices, and utilizing systems thinking to handle challenges that link administrative procedures to student growth. They are also accountable for overseeing the performance of the organization. It also shows

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that leading the change and having innovative leadership will help the management of the school successful in some aspects.

As a summary, the domains of the Performance of the respondents reveal that respondents are organized as they have a weighted mean of **3.88** and a verbal description of **distinguished** as visible on the data it shows that all the indicators under this domain have been rated properly. As a result, the respondents improve their ability to perform their duties and accomplish their tasks as leaders. To ensure that more ground is covered in providing high-quality education to the satisfaction of all stakeholders, it is necessary to have good management skills and organization skills, and it may lead to successful and systematized leadership. The importance of high-quality education and how it should be managed ensures that more ground is covered.

4. Correlations

4.1 Correlations between Demographic Profile and Competency Goals

Table 13 displays the correlation between the competency goals of SEAMEO ICeXeL Completers, namely strategic thinking and innovation, managerial leadership, instructional leadership, personal excellence, and stakeholder engagement, and their demographic profile, which includes age, gender, civil status, number of years managing the current school, position, and educational attainment.

Table 13

Correlations between Demographic Profile and Competency Goals of the Respondents

This table below depicts the relationship between respondents' demographic profile (age, gender, and civil status), number of years managing the current school, position and educational objectives, and competency goals in strategic thinking and innovation, managerial leadership, instructional leadership, personal excellence, and stakeholder engagement. The table shows the correlation coefficients (r) and significance levels (Sig.) for each variable.

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		Age	Sex	Civil Status	No. of Years in the School	Position	Educational Attainment
Strategic Thinking and Innovation	Pearson Correlation	-.346	-.290	-.639**	.189	-.167	.265
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.057	.114	.000	.309	.369	.150
	N	31	31	31	31	31	31
Managerial Leadership	Pearson Correlation	-.011	-.234	.043	.101	.238	.032
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.954	.205	.820	.590	.197	.865
	N	31	31	31	31	31	31
Instructional Leadership	Pearson Correlation	.008	-.103	-.141	.183	-.477**	-.126
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.966	.582	.450	.324	.007	.498
	N	31	31	31	31	31	31
Personal Excellence	Pearson Correlation	.229	.211	-.062	-.222	-.276	-.252
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.215	.255	.740	.230	.133	.171
	N	31	31	31	31	31	31
Stakeholders' Engagement	Pearson Correlation	-.112	.369*	-.083	.052	-.139	.031
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.548	.041	.655	.780	.455	.870
	N	31	31	31	31	31	31

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The study found a negative correlation between respondents' civil status and strategic thinking and creativity ($r = -.639$, $p < 0.01$). The result of $r = -.639$ indicates a significant negative association, implying that the variables tend to move in opposite directions. This suggests that the civil status of the completers has a strong relationship with their **strategic thinking and innovation**, which indicates that SEAMEO ICeL completers with single marital status or no commitment tend to have more strategic thinking and innovation. There was no significant correlation between respondents' demographic profile of age, sex number of years managing the present school, position and educational attainment with their strategic thinking and innovation.

The results revealed that age, sex, civil status, number of years in the position, position and educational was not significantly related to **managerial leadership**.

Moreover, the position of the respondents was found negatively significant at **instructional leadership** ($r = -.477$, $p < 0.01$). The value of $r = -.477$ denotes a negative relationship, this suggests that the position of the completers has inverse relationship with their instructional leadership, which indicates that SEAMEO ICeL completers' position tend to have better or lesser instructional leadership. There was no significant correlation

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between respondents' demographic profile of age, sex, civil status, number of years managing the present school, and educational attainment and their instructional leadership.

There was no significant correlation between respondents' demographic profile of age, sex, civil status, number of years managing the present school, position and educational attainment and their **personal excellence**. This indicates that the demographic profile of the SEAMEO IEXCeL completers' is not related to their personal excellence.

Similarly, there was no significant correlation between respondents' demographic profile of age, sex, civil status number of years managing the present school, position and educational attainment and their **stakeholders' engagement** which implies that the demographic profile of the SEAMEO IEXCeL completers' is not related to their stakeholders' engagement.

In conclusion, this study showed that SEAMEO IEXCeL completers' demographic profile of civil status is related to strategic thinking and innovation competence, also, position is related to instructional leadership. Therefore, policy makers and educator planners consider the school heads profiles when developing program to provide instructional support.

4.2 Correlations between Demographic Profile and Performance

The table below presents the correlation between SEAMEO IEXCeL Completers demographic profile (age, sex, civil status, the number of years managing the present school, position and educational attainment) and their performance.

Table 14
Correlations between Demographic Profile and Performance

	Age	Sex	Civil Status	No. of Years in the School	Position	Educational Attainment
Performance Pearson Correlation	.103	-.100	-.109	-.170	-.086	-.132
Sig. (2-tailed)	.580	.592	.560	.362	.645	.478
N	31	31	31	31	31	31

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 14 shows the association between the completers' demographic profile (age, gender, civil status, number of years managing the current school, position, and education) and performance. This table displays the correlation coefficients (r) and significance levels (Sig.) for each variable.

According to the findings, there was no significant relationship between respondents' performance and their demographic profile of age, gender, civil status, number of years managing the current school, position, or educational achievement.

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This suggests that the demographic profile of SEAMEO ICXeL participants has nothing to do with their performance.

4.3 Correlations between Competency Goals and Performance

Table 15 presents the correlation between SEAMEO ICXeL Completers' competency goals in their strategic thinking and innovation, managerial leadership, instructional leadership, personal excellence and stakeholders' engagement and their performance.

Table 15
Correlations between Competency Goals and Performance

		Strategic Thinking & Innovation	Managerial Leadership	Instructional Leadership	Personal Excellence	Stakeholders' Excellence
Performance	Pearson Correlation	.132	.211	.215	.493**	.042
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.480	.254	.246	.005	.822
	N	31	31	31	31	31

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table above shows the relationship between the SEAMEO ICXeL completers' **competency goals** and their **performance**. It also presents the correlation coefficients (*r*) and significance levels (Sig.) for each variable.

The computed value of $r = .493$, $p < 0.01$ revealed that there was positive significant relationship between the completers' **personal excellence** and performance. The value of $r = .483$ implies a positive relationship, which suggests that the personal excellence of the respondents has a relationship with their performance. This indicates that SEAMEO ICXeL completers with higher personal excellence tend to have higher performance.

The strategic thinking and innovation, managerial leadership, instructional leadership, and stakeholder engagement and performance of SEAMEO ICXeL graduates were not shown to be significantly correlated. This suggests that the performance of SEAMEO ICXeL graduates is unaffected by their strategic thinking and innovation, management leadership, instructional leadership, and stakeholder involvement.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the data, the following conclusion were drawn.

1. Majority of respondents were at the age of 31- 40 years old and 41-50 years old, majority of them are female, most of them were married, majority of them serve

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in the present school for 1-2 years, majority were school heads and the most of them were doctoral graduates.

2. The completers were distinguished in Strategic thinking and Innovation, distinguished in Managerial Leadership, as well as in Instructional Leadership, they were also distinguished in Personal Excellence and in Stakeholder engagement.
3. It was found that the SEAMEO IEXCeL completers were distinguished in all domains of their performance.
4. In the correlation of demographic profile and competency goals, there was a negatively strong significant correlation between civil status and strategic thinking and innovation and a negatively significant relationship between position and Instructional Leadership.

However, there was no discernible correlation between the respondents' performance and their demographic profile.

In the meantime, there was a strong positive correlation between the completers' performance and personal excellence.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the succeeding recommendations are hereby given.

1. School heads with distinguished competency and distinguished performance are critical for the success of the school. To help them excel and further improve their schools, attend leadership training and other professional development opportunities.
2. It is also highly recommended that the SEAMEO completers should adopt innovative practices.
3. Foster partnerships with local businesses, non-profits, and other educational institutions to create more opportunities for students and staff.
4. Completers are encouraged to have a long-term vision in strategic planning, resource management, and curriculum instruction.
5. Policy Makers and educators are encouraged to review and consider the demographic profile, competency, and performance of the school heads before making decisions or planning decisions.
6. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct further research and evaluation on the matter to gain a deeper understanding of these relationships, conduct longitudinal studies and qualitative research to explore causality and identify additional factors that may influence school heads' competencies and performance.

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